

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

MUSEUMS OF JAPAN

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Abstract: This article contains information about the famous museums of Japan. The history of the origin of each museum, its exhibits, historical items are mentioned separately. Sunny country-Japan has many places where cultural recreation is possible, no matter what time of year. The collection of installations of Yayoi Kusama, the tallest Museum in the world, sculpture gardens and islands of art will captivate you.

Key words: Japan, museum, history, information, tourist, delegation, National, Art, item, traditional, shrine, shrine, exhibition hall.

Sunny country-Japan has many places where cultural recreation is possible, no matter what time of year. The collection of installations of Yayoi Kusama, the tallest Museum in the world, sculpture gardens and the islands of art will surely charm you. Yayoi Kusama, a well-known representative of modern painting in the country, has a personal museum, which was established in 2017 with his active participation. This museum reopened in 2020, after a two-year break: tickets must be pre-ordered via the internet. The museum includes the last works of the artist not exhibited in Japan and abroad. Until the end of March, the museum can enjoy one of Kusama's biggest hits of the last decade — his psychological work “the infinity of the Mirrored Room”. The museum menu also includes the artist's new work “the bouquet of flowers”.

The idea of turning small islands in the Seto Inland Sea into an art archipelago came to the mind of entrepreneur and billionaire Soichiro Fukutake in the mid-80s, when the Japanese economy was at its peak. The two corporations, Benesse Holdings, Inc and Fukutake Foundation, started working in partnership with contemporary artists, prominent architects and sculptors. As a result of their efforts, the nature of the islands took on the appearance of art surrealism.

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Usually, tourists go to Hakone to enjoy nature: a forest covered with Moss, a quiet lake, fresh air of a calm Pine Grove. Now add a hundred open types of art installations to these beauties: from sculptures by Rodin, Miro and Henry Moore to complex works by modern artists. The open-air Hakone museum is organized on an area of 70,000 square meters, where you will find the perfect harmony of art.

Another amazing open — air museum is located on the North Island of Hokkaido. People come here in the warm season (the museum works from April to November): there are 74 works of art here for a walk through the forest full of works of art. Some installations are retrofuturistic in style and difficult to understand. And some perfectly reflect the Japanese mentality.

The Mori art Museum is an art collection located at the top as it is housed in a 54-story building in the Roppongi district of Tokyo. The museum does not have a permanent collection, on the contrary, the expositions are constantly changing, the site receives new projects and exhibitions. The museum was closed all winter due to renovations, but is scheduled to reopen from April 22 of that year.

Fukushima is a city-museum that proudly announces the opening of the city, fully recovering from the terrible disaster of 2011. The graffiti on the central streets made the city an open-air museum of Contemporary Art. If you are interested in street art, it is clear that this city is exactly youbop.

The Micah museum is located in the khushmanzara mountains of Sigaraki, in an area not far from the historical capital of Japan, Kyoto.

Next to the site of the museum are the ruins of Sigaraki-no Miya, the ancient capital of Japan, the Palace of the Emperor of Syomu (744-745 BC), who for some time moved the capital Nara.) is located at. The museum was founded in 1997 by Mrs. Koyama Mihoko (1910-2003), a benihoya appreciation of beauty.

The passage of the museum with the tunnel to the main building is connected by steel ropes with a light lift bridge 120 meters long, through which it passes to the main building. Eighty percent of the museum building is underground, leaving no shadow on the mountain landscape. And in the eyes

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of the viewer is thrown only a small entrance pavilion, which embodies Japanese and Chinese modern architecture.

The State Museum of the history of Uzbekistan of the ozr FA is the largest museum that conducts research in various fields of historiography of Uzbekistan. In 2018, The Museum of history of Uzbekistan signed an agreement with the Museum of the University of Tokyo, Japan (Museum, Tokyo University) to cooperate in the field of research of archaeological monuments of the stone age for a 5-year period (2018-2022). Currently, joint research is being carried out in cooperation with these two museums in the south of Uzbekistan (Yakkabog and Kitab District of Kashkadarya region), as well as in the Nurota mountains of Navoi region and Boysun District of Surkhandarya region.

After the conclusion of the U.S.-Japan Friendship Treaty in 1858, the Japanese delegation to America began to directly observe Western-style museums.

After the Meiji Restoration, botanist Keysuke Ito and naturalist Tanaka Yoshio also wrote about the need to create museum objects from objects found in the West. Preparations began for the construction of structures to preserve historical monuments of the past.

In 1872, the Museum of the Ministry of Education held Japan's first exhibition in the Yusima area of Tokyo. Minerals, fossil remains, animals, plants, regional crafts and artifacts are among the Featured Articles.

In 1877, an educational museum (Kyoiku Hakubutsukan línínínín) was opened in the Ueno Park (now the National Science Museum of Japan) with exhibitions dedicated to physics, chemistry, zoology, botany and regional crafts. As part of the exhibition, art objects were also displayed in the “Museum of art”.

The Imperial Household department oversaw the establishment of a central museum dedicated to historical artifacts in 1886. In addition, in the years after 1877, there was a great enthusiasm for establishing regional museums in Akita, Niigata, Kanazawa, Kyoto, Osaka, and Hiroshima.

The Nara National Museum opened its doors in 1895 and the Kyoto National Museum in 1897 [2]. Other national specialized museums were: the

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Department of Agriculture and Commerce exhibition hall (1897), the Patent Office exhibition hall (1905), and the Postal Museum (1902).

In 1925, the Imperial Household museum, part of the collection of the Tokyo National Museum, was allocated to the science and historical monument departments. Categorization was a step towards creating an art museum.

In addition to national museums, private museums were also established after the turn of the century. The first private museum was The Okura Shukokan museum, built in 1917 to house The Okura Kihachiro collection. Industrialist Oxara Mogasaburo founded the Oxara Art Museum in 1930 in Kurashiki, Okayama prefecture. The museum was the first Japanese museum dedicated to Western art.

By 1945 there were 150 museums in Japan. However, the Great Kanto Earthquake (1923), Sino-Japanese war and World War II led to stagnation of Japanese museum activities.

Japanese art objects were collected in Shosōin (treasure houses) of shrines and temples dating back to the Nara period. The artifacts were included in the National hakubutsukan established during the Meiji period, but were not included in the separate category of the art museum (bijutsukan língín) until 1945.

After World War II[edit / edit source]

Plans for museums that had been shelved during the war were revived in the 1950s. Kyoiku Hakubutsukan became the National Science Museum of Japan (Kokuritsu Kagaku Hakubutsukan) in 1949, and the former Monbusho Hakubutsukan became the National Museum of Tokyo (Tokyo Kokuritsu Hakubutsukan 25.

The government focused on the development of the Art Museum in the post-war period, opening the National Museum of Modern Art (Tokyo Kokuritsu Kindai Bijutsukan) in Tokyo, which houses Japanese and foreign art.

Private museums were still opened after the war. In 1966, the Yamatane Art Museum and the Idemitsu art gallery were established, both built around private collections.

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In the 1970s, prefectural and local authorities began opening museums and art museums dedicated to the traditional arts and crafts or commerce of their individual communities. The 1980s saw a national explosion in the development of the new art museum, with 90 new objects built in 1988 alone.

Local governments were active in establishing many of these museums. In addition, museums dedicated to individual areas of industry have been established, among them the Denryokukan língínín electricity Museum, 1984) and the Metro Museum (Chikatetsu Hakubutsukan 1986).

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